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DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

Fighting with a Smile: Satirical and Humourist Voices of Resilience from Hindi Speaking Subaltern Subjects and Communities

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DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

PROJECT	
Project number:	Call Horizon Europe: 101152854
Project acronym:	FISM
Project name:	Fighting with a Smile: Satirical and Humourist Voices of Resilience from Hindi Speaking Subaltern Subjects and Communities
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1. Introduction

This document shows the Data Management Plan of the project FISM, “Fighting with a Smile: Satirical and Humourist Voices of Resilience from Hindi Speaking Subaltern Subjects and Communities”. FISM project investigates the uses and functions of humour and satire in the Indian contemporary context. The project points at explaining how these modes are currently being used by Indian authors as cultural assets to pursue strategies of resilience, activism and self-empowerment. The research interrogates the relationship between comedy and marginalities. It analyses in an interdisciplinary, organic way how cultural areas such as literature, performative arts and new media are currently crucial instruments to mobilize social engagement and to produce a variety of adaptive coping strategies. The research has the distinctive feature of focusing on the uses of humour and satire in Indian languages. Another important aspect regards the study of subaltern and marginalized groups and communities. These terms are used in the research to refer to authors belonging to Dalit, Adivasi, LGBTQIA +.

The aim of the DMP is to provide information about the life cycle of data in the context of the project, from generation to preservation, sharing and re-use. It also provides information on the ethical and legal framework of the research. The document is based on the FAIR principles, as articulated in the "FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship", 2016, which provide guidelines for improving the discoverability, accessibility, interoperability and reuse of research data. The report used to prepare this document follows the template provided by the European Commission. It is a 'living' document and will be updated throughout the research life cycle in line with any significant changes in data management.

2. Data Summary

The present data summary is intended to provide information about the following aspects related to the data management in the course of the project:

- Information about the re-use or generation of the data.
- Types and formats of data that are generated or re-used.
- Purpose of data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project.
- Origin/provenance of the data.
- Data utility outside the objectives of the FISM project.

The data generated in the research are qualitative and, in a more limited way, also quantitative. They reflect the theoretical objectives as envisaged by the Principal Investigator of the research, in the project proposal. The generated data are of different nature: they are primarily textual and audiovisual. In a more marginal way, they could also entail, especially in the realization of research tasks which imply extraction of data from social media, the collection of quantitative and numerical data. The majority of the data are generated during the first two years of the outgoing phase of the FISM project. In a more limited way, other data are generated during the return-phase of the project. Data are generated through different methods, that imply: A) Participant Observation during performative events; B) Critical Study of literary and extra-literary sources; C) Audiovisual Recording; D) Data Collection and Data Analysis of social media materials. In addition, data are generated during the realization of activities of communication, social engagement and dissemination of the research. The PI makes the research data available in Zenodo, used as a trusted repository, in open or with restricted access to allow accessibility, reusability and long-term preservation. All the data will be also conserved on external drives and on pCloud, that can also realize the backup in an automatic way (See section 6. Security). The following datasets will be generated during the research:

Dataset references	Dataset 1
Dataset name	FISM, WP1. Interviews to Indian performers
Team in charge	Fabio Mangraviti (PI)
Description of the data that are generated or collected	The dataset stems from open-ended interviews to literary writers and performers connected to the areas of satire and humour in India. The interviews, initially recorded by the PI by using an audio recorder, are later transcribed. After that, the audio recordings are erased.
Function	Interview is needed as a <i>qualitative</i> method of the research for collecting observations by participants.
Format	Word text format (doc.).
Data volume	The data are in the range of maximum 500 KB.
Potential users	Target audience includes scholars active in the area of the South Asian studies, particularly those with an interest in the fields of Indian literatures, performative studies and society.
Accessibility and re-use	The entire dataset will be openly accessible and stored on Zenodo, used as a trusted repository in research, under a CC BY licence by the end of the 18th month. The dataset will be continuously updated with new documentation throughout the duration of the project.
Keywords	Satire, humour, interviews.
Status	In progress.

Dataset references	Dataset 2
Dataset name	FISM. WP3. Critical study of Hindi literary texts.
Team in charge	Fabio Mangraviti
Description of the data that are generated or collected	Critical study of Hindi literary texts. The analysis, based on the study of prose and poetry production by Dalit, Adivasi, LGBTQIA+ and women writers, focuses on the use of humorous and satirical elements by the authors.
Function	Critical study of literary texts is needed as a <i>qualitative</i> method to generate data on the use of humour and satire by modern Hindi writers.
Format	Word text format (doc.).
Data volume	The data are in the range of maximum 500 KB.
Potential users	The target audience includes scholars in the area of South Asian studies, particularly those engaged in the study of Dalit, Adivasi and LGBTQIA+ literatures in India.
Accessibility and re-use	The entire dataset will be openly accessible in Zenodo, used as a trusted repository in the research, under a CC BY licence by the end of the 28th month of the research.

Keywords	Hindi literature, Dalit, Adivasi, women writers.
Status	In progress.

Dataset references	Dataset 3
Dataset name	FISM. WP2. Participation in performative comedy-related events.
Team in charge	Fabio Mangraviti
Description of the data that are generated or collected	Critical study of the texts performed by Indian humourists in the course of four stand-up comedy shows and one Hasya kavi sammelan. The dataset also includes notes and observations collected during participant observation. The personal data collected during the realization of this dataset contains the name and personal views of the writers interviewed.
Function	Participant observation and the study of texts by performative practitioners are two important <i>qualitative</i> methods for generating data on the performative life of humour and satire in the contemporary Indian context.
Format	Word text format (doc.).
Data volume	The data are considered to be in the range of maximum 500 KB.
Potential users	Scholars in the field of South Asian Studies, particularly those working on Dalit, Adivasi and LGBTQIA+ literatures in India.
Accessibility and re-use	The entire dataset will be made available and openly stored on Zenodo, used as a trusted repository in the research, under a CC BY licence by the end of the 24th month of the research. The first half of the dataset will be stored on Zenodo by the end of the 12 th month and the second half by the end of the 24 th month.
Keywords	Stand-up comedy, Hindi, Hinglish, Dalit, LGBTQIA+, Adivasi, women.
Status	In progress.

Dataset references	Dataset 4
Dataset name	FISM. WP4. Gathering and analysis of comedy-related sources on social-media and networks.
Team in charge	Fabio Mangraviti
Description of the data that are generated or collected	The dataset contains <i>qualitative</i> and <i>quantitative</i> data. It consists of the raw and processed data generated through the extraction and analysis of memes published on Instagram pages. The dataset may, but will not necessarily, also include data generated through the use of AI software. Both the collected and analysed data (both qualitative and quantitative) are aggregated and anonymized.
Function	The generation of this dataset is necessary to investigate the digital life of humour on social media, with a focus on Instagram.
Format	Word text format (doc.)
Data volume	The data are considered to be in the range of maximum 500 KB.
Potential users	The target audience include scholars in the area of South Asian studies and/or interested in the study of the 'meme culture' in the South Asian area.

Accessibility and re- Data analysis of five Hindi literary sources	A first half of the dataset will be made available and stored in open access on Zenodo, used as a trusted repository in the research, under CC BY license, by the end of the 24 th month; a second dataset will stored on Zenodo by the end of the 33 th month of the research.
Keywords	Meme, Hindi, Hinglish, Dalit, Adivasi, LGBTQIA+.
Status	In progress.

Dataset references	Dataset 5
Dataset name	FISM. WP2. Video-recording of four stand-up comedy shows and one Hasya kavi sammelan.
Team in charge	Fabio Mangraviti
Description of the data that are generated or collected	It includes the video-recording of four shows by stand-up comedy shows and (at least) one Hasya kavi sammelan.
Function	The video-recording is a <i>qualitative</i> research method used to facilitate the realization of the data analysis (see Dataset 3); further, it may be used in activities of communication and dissemination of the results of the research.
Format	Typical file format used for this data is MP4.
Data volume	The data are considered in the range of maximum 20 GB.
Potential users	The target audience includes scholars in the area of South Asian studies and/or scholars interested the study of stand-up comedy in India and in other global contexts. Also, the data may be of interest to the general public and/or to stakeholders interested in the relationship between comedy and social activism.
Accessibility and re-use.	The dataset will be made available and stored with restricted access on Zenodo, which will be used as a trusted repository in the research, under a CC BY NC ND licence by the end of the 28 th month of the research. The dataset will be progressively built and updated throughout the project as data is generated.
Keywords	Stand-up comedy, Hinglish, comedy shows.
Status	In progress.

Dataset references	Dataset 6
Dataset name	FISM. WP2. Video-recording of Holi performances in Kumaon.
Team in charge	Fabio Mangraviti
Description of the data that are generated or collected	The dataset is based on audio recordings made in the Kumaon region of India. The research will focus in particular on the Mahila Holi, a performative event that takes place in the months of February and March, during which women from the region perform texts with a satirical and humorous value. The data will be collected in an anonymous manner.
Function	The video-recording is needed as a <i>qualitative</i> method to support the realization of tasks of data analysis and, if made possible by certain ethical and juridical conditions, may be used in the communication and dissemination of the results of the research.
Format	Typical file format used for this data is MP4
Data volume	The data are considered in the range of maximum 20 GB.
Potential users	The target audience may include scholars in the area of

	South Asian studies and/or scholars interested in the study of performative traditions in India and in other global contexts
Accessibility and re-use	The dataset will be made available and stored with restricted access on Zenodo, used as a trusted repository in the research, under CC BY NC ND license, by the end of the 28th month of the research.
Keywords	Holi, Mahila holi.
Status	In progress.

Dataset references	Dataset 7
Dataset name	FISM. WP6. Organization of a 'Humour festival' in India.
Team in charge	Fabio Mangraviti
Description of the data that are generated or collected	The dataset encompasses materials produced before and during the realization of a festival. It may include reports, a brochure, posters, video-recordings.
Function	The generation of this dataset is necessary to the organization of a Humor festival in India. The function of the festival is to communicate the results of the research. It is also useful to strengthen the network of the PI.
Format	Word text format (doc.); Video-recordings (MP4), PDF.
Data volume	The data are considered in the range of maximum of 10 GB.
Potential users	The target audience includes scholars in the area of South Asian studies and/or interested in the study of the performative traditions in India and in other global contexts.
Accessibility and re-use	The dataset will be made available and stored on Zenodo, used as a trusted repository in the research, under CC BY licence, after the realization of the event.
Keywords	Festival, Humour, Hindi.
Status	In progress.

Dataset references	Dataset 8
Dataset name	FISM. WP2. Data analysis of texts performed during Holi.
Team in charge	Fabio Mangraviti
Description of the data that are generated or collected	The dataset consists of the analysis, based on the notes acquired during the participant observation and critical study of the performed texts, of the performances occurring during Holi in the Kumaon region every in the months of February and March. All the data will be collective and anonymous.
Function	The dataset serves for realizing the WP2 of the project, named "Participation in performative comedy-related events".
Format	Word text format (doc.)
Data volume	The data are considered in the range of maximum 500kb.
Potential users	The target audience includes scholars in the area of South Asian studies and/or interested in the study of the performative traditions in India and in other global contexts.
Accessibility and re-use	The dataset will be made available and stored with restricted access on Zenodo, used as a trusted repository in the research, under CC BY NC SA license, by the end of the 28th month of the research.

Keywords	Holi, mahila holi, Kumaon.
Status	In progress.

Dataset references	Dataset 9
Dataset name	FISM. Website management dataset
Team in charge	Fabio Mangraviti
Description of the data that are generated or collected	Reports that describe the procedures of creation and management of the Website of the project FISM. Images and podcasts uploaded on the Website.
Function	The dataset provides information about the procedures of creation and management of the website of the project FISM, functional at the communication of the results of the research to the general public.
Format	HTML, Word Text format (doc.), MP4.
Data volume	The data are considered in the range of maximum 20 GB.
Potential users	The Website is intended to communicate the main objectives and results of the research to the general public.
Accessibility and re-use	The website is already available in open access and can be found at the following link: https://fismproject.com/ . A report describing the website is available in Zenodo in open-access and under CC BY licence.
Keywords	Fism project, Website.
Status	In progress.

Dataset references	Dataset 10
Dataset name	FISM. WP6. Communication activities of the FISM project.
Team in charge	Fabio Mangraviti
Description of the data that are generated or collected	Reports that describe the activities of communication conducted in the course of the project. Powerpoints used to realize the activities.
Function	The activities of communication are necessary to prove the social engagement of the research. Moreover, they testify the efforts made by the researcher to maximize the impact of the research.
Format	Word text format (doc.) ; PPs.
Data volume	500 kb.
Potential users	The target audience includes scholars in the area of South Asian studies and/or interested in the study of the performative traditions in India and in other global contexts.
Accessibility and re-use	The dataset will be updated with new documentation throughout the project. All the data will be stored on Zenodo, used as a trusted repository, under CC BY licence. The data will be progressively updated in the course of the research.
Keywords	Fism project, Website.
Status	In progress.

Dataset references	Dataset 11
Dataset name	FISM. Focus Group.
Team in charge	Fabio Mangraviti
Description of the data that are generated or collected	Transcription of the personal opinions on the uses, aesthetics and socio-cultural functions of humour

	expressed by participants in a focus group. Before being transcribed, the data are previously audio recorded. After the transcription, the recordings are erased. All the personal data will be collected in a collective and anonymous way.
Function	Data collection. Organization of joint-activities of dissemination and communication of the research.
Format	Word text format (doc.)
Data volume	500 KB.
Potential users	The target audience includes scholars in the area of South Asian studies and/or interested in the study of the performative traditions in India and in other global contexts.
Accessibility and re-use	A report be available and stored on Zenodo, used as a trusted repository, under CC BY licence, by the end of the 32th month of the project.
Keywords	Focus group.

Dataset references	Dataset 12
Dataset name	FISM. Training activities.
Team in charge	Fabio Mangraviti
Description of the data that are generated or collected	Reports of the training activities.
Function	Presentation of the development of the research and training activities carried out by the PI.
Format	Word text format (doc.)
Data volume	500 KB
Potential users	The target audience includes scholars in the area of South Asian studies and/or interested in the study of the performative traditions in India and in other global contexts.
Accessibility and re-use	The data will be progressively updated in the course of the research. A first dataset
Keywords	Training activities.

Apart from the above-mentioned datasets, the PI plans to generate during the research these types of data:

Type of data	Format(s) used during data processing	Format(s) for sharing, reuse
Scientific articles (WP5)	PDF	Open access storage on Zenodo, used as a trusted repository, under the CC BY licence.
Pre-print version of the articles (WP5)	PDF	Open access storage on Zenodo, used as a trusted repository, under the CC BY licence.
Other reports	Word text format (doc.)	Open access storage on Zenodo, used as a trusted repository, under the CC BY licence.
Data Management Plan (WP8)	PDF	Open access storage on Zenodo, used as a trusted repository, under the CC BY licence.

Plan for the dissemination and exploitation of the results (WP8)	PDF	Open access storage on Zenodo, used as a trusted repository, under the CC BY licence.
Career Development Plan (WP8)	PDF	Sensitive and restricted report to be uploaded to the EU-funded Funding and Tenders Portal.

Alongside the *generation* of the above-mentioned data, the project entails the production, during its whole duration, of metadata describing all the data generated (see 2.1). All the metadata are stored on Zenodo, used as a trusted repository in the research, under CC0 licence. According to Francis' definition of 'reuse' "data are reused when they are collected for one use and then used a second time" (2017). From this perspective, at the present stage the research does not entail the re-use of main data previously generated in other researches. Nonetheless, to achieve the main results of the research, the PI employs a variety of primary and secondary sources. Among them, the PI collects and investigates primary and secondary sources in Hindi and in other Indian languages, with a focus on journals, literary texts and other written materials. In addition, the generation of data also involves the study of material extracted from social media, such as YouTube and Instagram, in order to achieve some of the main theoretical objectives of the research (see, for example, Dataset 3, entitled 'Data analysis of meme in Hinglish').

As the above-mentioned tables reflecting datasets showcase, part of data to be generated by the project consists in the information which may identify natural persons (namely, "personal data" according to the definition of the Article 2, no. 1, GDPR)". The following tables showcase the type of personal data as envisaged in the project, their origin and the way in which all the envisaged personal data are stored and re-used in the project:

Description of personal data	Origin of the personal data	Anonymization and other measures.	Accessibility and reuse
Names of Participants	Interviews, activities of communication and dissemination, video-recordings of the performative events.	All the sensitive data will be anonymized.	Data will be available and stored on Zenodo, used as a trusted repository, in CC BY licence.
Personal opinions	Interviews, activities of communication and dissemination, video recordings of the performative events.	All the data will be anonymized.	Data will be available and stored on Zenodo, used as a trusted repository, in CC BY licence.
Video-recordings of participants.	Video-recordings of the performative events.	All the sensitive data will be anonymized.	Data will be available and stored on Zenodo, used as a trusted repository, in CC BY NC ND licence.

3. FAIR data

3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

All the data that are stored on Zenodo are identified by a DOI, used as persistent identifier. Zenodo is compliant with the standards Dublin Core, that is a general-purpose metadata vocabulary for describing data of any kind. It is also based on the DataCite Metadata Schema v4. The mission of DataCite is to build and maintain a sustainable framework that makes it possible to cite data through the use of persistent identifiers. The storage of the metadata follows the general standards as indicated in the OpenAire 3.0, whose objective is to provide a metadata schema and provide interoperability through a

small number of properties - making interoperability possible in the simplest manner possible and as a result keep the technical barriers for implementation as low as possible. Given the interdisciplinary nature of the research, the choice of metadata also takes into account the best practices of previous research in the field of South Asian studies. The metadata associated with the data to make them findable *always* include:

1. Identifier (a unique string that identifies the resource)
2. Creator/s (name of the researchers involved in the creation of the data)
3. Title (a name by which the data is known)
4. Publisher (the name of the entity that holds, archives, publishes, prints, distributes, releases, the resource)
5. Publication data (format YYYY-MM-DD)
6. Resource type
7. Description
8. Version
9. Access right (open, restricted; if the access to the data is restricted, the conditions to get access)
10. Licence
11. Keywords
12. Funding reference

In addition to these metadata, the PI *may* also decide to add other metadata, that, in compliance with the OpenAire 3.0, will regard:

1. Format
2. Size
3. Language
4. Geolocation
5. Contributor.

To *label* the datasets the PI uses the following scheme: Creator (PublicationYear): Title. Version. Publisher. ResourceType. Identifier (as indicated in the document “DataCite Metadata Schema Documentation for the Publication and Citation of Research Data”, 2016). To *label* the documents associated with the datasets the PI uses the following scheme: DATASETname_Acronym-WPnumber_coverage or other content specifications date (YYYYMMDD)_vn. file extension. To optimize the possibility of discovering and the re-use of the data/meta-data, all the dataset are reposit by adopting key-words, that describe the content of the data and let the re-use of the project by other scholars with and interest (or not) in the area of the South Asian studies. All the metadata are offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed. To enhance the possibility of *indexation* the project pursues the following best practices: 1) Indexation frequency; 2) Avoiding overcomplication; 3) Regular monitoring and Evaluation; 4) Use of a transparent language; 5) engagement with other figures (i.e. international office at the beneficiary institution; coordinator; other scholars in the area of the South Asian studies).

3.2 Making data accessible

Repository

All data and metadata are stored on Zenodo, which is used as a *trusted* and *secure* repository in the project. They will be stored here for five years after the end of the FISM project. At this stage, the project does not involve depositing the data and metadata in other general or specific repositories. The trusted and secure nature of the platform is demonstrated by the fact that it is managed by CERN (Conseil européen pour la nuclear research) for OPENAIRE (Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe) to facilitate self-archiving by researchers who have the rights to publish in open data. Users are identified using Mendeley, ORCID (Open Researcher and Contributor ID), OpenAIRE. Each contribution is *identified* by a specific DOI (Digital Object Identifier), with bibliographic references exportable in BibTeX, DataCite, DC, EndNote, NLM, RefWorks MARC and MARCXML formats. Measurement of the impact of the publication via Altmetric. The platform allows raw data to be deposited at any stage of research, for sharing with consortium laboratories in separate experiments. Indexing is guaranteed by the standard Oai Pmh protocol. Content is publicly available under any of the 400 open licenses (from opendefinition.org and spdx.org). Support for confidential content is also possible.

Metadata will be *freely* retained for the lifetime of the repository, which is as long as CERN exists. Another reason for which Zenodo has been selected by the PI is that it accepts *large file sizes*, up to 50 GB for any dataset without any involved cost and with the possibility to extend it. This is an important consideration as any datasets generated during the project will not exceed the expected file size. Zenodo can accept up to 100 datasets. This allows the PI to deposit on Zenodo all the datasets generated during the FISM project.

Data

The PI is owner and responsible for the use of the generated data. All the data generated during the research are *stored* on Zenodo in compliance with the H2020 Program Guidelines on FAIR Data, which provides guidelines to improve the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse of digital assets. Following these guidelines all data are made “as open as possible and as closed as necessary”: “open” in order to foster the reusability and to accelerate research, but also “closed” to safeguard the privacy of the subjects. Additional provisions on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data have been endorsed by the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), Reg. (EU) 2016/679.

Data Risks, restrictions and protocol of accessibility to the data.

In the light of the above-mentioned guidelines and regulations, it is worth noting that the datasets 5 (Video-recording of four stand-up comedy shows in Hindi, Hinglish), dataset 6 (Video-recording of Hasya kavi sammelan), dataset 7 (Video-recording of Holi performances in Kumaon), may entail the generation of sensitive personal. For this reason, they are stored with *restricted access* on Zenodo. The sensitive character of the data may derive from the content of the personal ideas expressed by authors of the participants whose images are generated and deposited in the dataset. Indeed, according to the European GDPR regulation “Special categories of personal data (formerly known as ‘sensitive data’) — Include personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation (Article 9(1) GDPR).” It is also relevant to note that, according to the FAIR data guidelines, the restriction on data sharing could derive from the right to preserve the “protection of personal data of key informants involved in surveys, focus groups, interviews, and case studies”. The risks related to the protection of personal data that could arise from granting access to the above-mentioned datasets are medium. Indeed, access to images and personal opinions of the participants, especially if they represent people belonging to marginalized or minor groups, could lead to forms of stigmatization and other ethical concerns for the participants.

Moreover, if the participants were to express ideas of political or philosophical value, the free and unrestricted sharing and re-use of the personal data (especially in the context of the video recordings) could, in the worst-case scenario, lead to legal consequences for the subjects. However, the likelihood of these risks materialising appears to be *low*. In fact, only a few artists working in the field of satire and humour have so far been exposed to the above-mentioned consequences. The impact of the risks varies according to the nature of the personal data collected during the research. The subjects belonging to smaller groups, especially if they are not well-known authors, could face more risks resulting from the research. The possible risks arising from the generation of data will be continuously monitored by the PI throughout the research.

To monitor them, the PI will be in constant contact with all participants, gatekeepers, NGOs and other policy-making institutions or stakeholders who are in contact with the participants. All participants will be able to contact the PI for any requests regarding the use of data in the research. In addition, in line with the guidelines suggested by researchers conducting fieldwork with marginalised communities in India (Potnis, Gala 2020), the PI will take a number of measures to avoid creating any form of risk for the participants in the research. Among them, it is worth *highlighting that all sensitive data of the research will be anonymized* (for the other measures, see the "Ethics" section below). If any of the identified risks were to occur, the PI and the host institution of the project (Sapienza University of Rome) will be committed to pursuing policy initiatives to support the participants at the institutional level, both at the national and international level. At this stage, we do not see *any risk related to intellectual property issues*. In view of the above, as mentioned above, the PI intends to upload the above-mentioned datasets with restricted access. However, both during and after the end of the project, access to the data will be possible *through a free and standardized access protocol*. The protocol will involve the realisation of the following iter. The protocol will entail the realization of the following work-flow:

1. Users can request access on Zenodo as authenticated users.
2. Fill in by writing their email address, full name, a message to the owner in which they clearly indicate the following information: 1) Name, title and institution/department of investigator; 2) Description of the proposed research that supports need to access the restricted-used data.
3. Tick the checkbox that they agree to that their personal data are shared with the record owner.
4. The requests are assessed by a ethics committee formed by the PI and the coordinator of the research at the beneficiary institution (Sapienza, University of Rome). The PI may also decide to consult other persons, in particular the ethics mentor and the data manager. In order to verify the identity of the users who made the request, the PI could send a private email to the email address of the latter and ask them to send a copy of their identity card by email.
5. The PI may also ask the participants whose personal data are included in the dataset if they agree to the data

being made available to the researchers requesting the data. Participants will be contacted by the PI primarily by email and/or mobile phone. If it is not possible to contact them by these means, the PI may contact gatekeepers and/or others who are in contact with the participants.

6. After a first screening of the requests by the committee, if the majority of the ethics board would agree, the data will be shared to the users who requested access.

As a general principle, the PI will make all the possible and legitimate actions and strategies will to allow the sharing of data on which there are restrictions. Apart from the above-mentioned protocol the PI pursues the following practices: 1) Cooperation and dialogue with the users who will request access to the data. If needed, the PI may also write to the e-mail address of the users to facilitate the transparency of the process; 2) When sources are freely available online in their original form, but direct reproduction is not permitted, the PI will provide detailed information about how the dataset was created from the original data; 3) Conversion of the data in standard open formats; 4) If the authorization to get access to the data would be denied, the PI will explain in detail reasons behind this choice to the users.

Quality of the data in terms of Standards, Calibration, Validation, Review

To preserve the coherence and quality of the research all the generated data (and, more in particular, those that entail qualitative data) the datasets will provide detailed informations about the way data have been collected, processed and/or re-used. The datasets will be realized by following good practices for qualitative research as described in detail by Kelley et al. (2003), “Good practice in the conduct and reporting of survey research”, and other sources (Akers 2013; Akers; Doty 2013; Edmond 2020; Research Council UK 2015; Warking 2007; Wilkinson et al. 2016; Woeber 2017, among others). All the qualitative data which entail the generation of personal data will:

1. Describe how, where participants were contacted;
2. Explain how many participants were contacted and how many participated”;
3. Give detailed informations about the purpose of the dataset, with identification of questions, objectives also in relationship with the WPs as articulated in the proposal of the project;
4. Explain the relevance of the data, also with reference to the previous contributions in the same area of studies;
5. Provide information about what type of attempts have been made to contact participants;
6. If relevant, provide information about how informed consent was obtained;
7. Describe in details the methods and obstacles encountered during the data analysis;
8. Present in a clear, concise and clear way the results of the research;
9. Providing conclusions and recommendations;
10. Providing a mapping to the vocabularies used in the data collection/analysis.

In order to ensure the validation and verification process of all data and metadata generated during the project, the PI will, at each stage of the project, consult the coordinator at the beneficiary institution and other individuals who will advise and/or assist the PI in the course of the research. The PI will be in constant contact with other scholars in the field of South Asian studies who will review and validate the datasets before they are deposited in the repository. The validation process will also involve the consultation of an ethics mentor to advise the PI on data management, a data manager and, if necessary, a legal advisor. In the case of validation of scientific publications, beneficiaries will provide (digital or physical) access as soon as possible to data or other results needed to validate the conclusions of scientific publications, provided that their legitimate interests or constraints are respected (and unless they have already provided (open) access at the time of publication (see "Horizon Europe, Annotated model Grant Agreement, Annex 5 -Art. 17"). A browser is all that is needed to access the project. The scripts, documentation and results can also be read with a simple text editor. The video recordings are accessed using a VLC media player.

Metadata

All the metadata will be made openly available and licence under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Agreement. The Metadata will remain available and findable also after the data will no longer be available as long as Zenodo will exist. The scripts, documentation and results will be readable through a simple text editor. A reference about the Mediaplayer will also be included in the metadata.

3.3 Making data interoperable

The standard descriptive metadata used in the generation of the data will be the DataCite Metadata Schema 4. DataCite Metadata Schema 4, as expressed in the document “DataCite Metadata Schema for the Publication and Citation of Research Data and Other Research Outputs. Version 4.6. DataCite e.V.”, produced by DataCite Metadata Working Group

(2024), is “a list of core metadata properties chosen for accurate and consistent identification of a resource for citation and retrieval purposes, with recommended use instructions in the documentation”.

The DataCite metadata schema has six DataCite mandatory properties, which include 1) identifier; 2) creator; 3) title; 4) publisher; 5) year of publication; 6) resource type. In addition, this model includes nineteen recommended and optional properties that may include Subject, Contributor, Date, Language, Alternate Identifier, RelatedIdentifier, Size, Format, Version, Rights, Description, GeoLocation, Funding Reference. The dataset will also include the metadata as specified in section 3.1 of this DMP. In order to make the data interoperable, the PI will also adopt community-endorsed best practices for interoperability, which may include (but are not limited to) the principles identified in the 'Guidance on best practice in the management of research data', a document produced by the Research Council UK (2015)

1. “Data with acknowledged long-term value should be preserved and remain accessible and usable for future research.” (ibid., 3)
2. “To enable research data to be discoverable and effectively re-used by others, sufficient metadata should be recorded and made openly available to enable other researchers to understand the research and re-use potential of the data. Published results should always include information on how to access the supporting data” (ibid.)
3. “Research data should be supported by sufficient contextual information to enable others to find what research data exist, why, when and how they were generated, and how to access them (i.e. metadata for discovery). This information should be made available online with terms that permit its full re-use.” (ibid., 4)
4. “Researchers should ensure that metadata created to support retained research datasets is sufficient to allow other researchers a reasonable understanding of those datasets and thereby minimise unintentional misuse, misinterpretation or confusion. For example, the metadata may need to describe the origin, processing, analysis and/or the researcher’s management of a dataset.” (ibid., 5)
5. To facilitate the interoperability of the data the PI will use vocabularies as suggested by official sources and institutions that suggest a common and interoperable.

One source for the development of the vocabulary will be Eurostat, the statistical office of the European Union. Other sources will be considered for the use of a vocabulary that can make research data and metadata interoperable by researchers from different research fields. As a general principle, the PI will provide a detailed mapping of the vocabulary used in the datasets in case it would be unavoidable to use uncommon or generate project-specific ontologies or vocabularies. At this stage, the PI does not plan to openly publish a dataset containing the generated ontologies and vocabularies. However, if the generation of the generated datasets makes this measure necessary, the PI will publish a specific dataset on Zenodo, openly accessible and under a CC BY licence, prior to the publication of the latter. There are currently no plans to include qualified references to other data, e.g. datasets from previous research.

3.4 Increase data re-use

To validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use the research provides different kinds of documentation. Among them, as analysed in detail in the section 3.2, the research intends to produce detailed information about the methodology used in the data collection, observations generated during the research, detailed data about the procedures followed to contact the participants and/or produce consents etc. Furthermore, the validation of the data analysis will also be made possible by the generation of data, such as video recordings, images and other useful data, which will be stored on Zenodo, in open and/or restricted access, in parallel with the generation of the data analysis and the data generated by the dissemination activities of the results. The majority of the useful documentation will be attached in single files attached to the distinct datasets (the format used will be the pdf, word, power points).

However, given their sensitive nature, it is worth recalling that the video recordings of the performances material that may identify the participants will be stored in separate datasets. With the exception of the video recordings, which will be stored under a CC BY NC ND licence, and the metadata (CC0 licence), all other datasets will be stored under a CC BY licence in order to allow the widest possible re-use. In line with the principle of “as open as possible and as closed as necessary”, data that may contain sensitive data or data that may raise ethical risks and concerns will be deposited in the repository with restricted access to allow sharing only under certain conditions in a protocol, as described in detail in section 3.2. All data produced during the project will be available for use by third parties. The ability to cite the data is provided by the rich metadata that will be offered to each of the datasets. The data and metadata derived from the research can be used by scholars, policy actors (e.g. NGOs) and other private and public actors (e.g. embassy cultural centres, museums) interested in studying the relationship between humour and activism in the South Asian region. The provenance of the data will be thoroughly documented in the research using the appropriate standards as provided in the DataCite metadata schema 4. In terms of quality assurance procedures, as stated in section 2.2, the PI will consult the coordinator and others who will advise him/her during the research to ensure validation at each stage of the project.

Validation also includes the appointment of an ethics mentor and a data manager to advise the PI on issues related to data management, data security and data protection in research. An ethics mentor has already been appointed by the PI; a data manager has also been appointed to advise the PI on data management, storage and security issues in the research. The PI may also consult a legal advisor on matters concerning the ethical and legal use of data in the research. The PI will publish a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript in Zenodo under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Public Licence (CC BY) at the latest at the time of publication. In the case of validation of scientific publications, the PI will provide access (digital or physical) as soon as possible to the data or other results needed to validate the conclusions of scientific publications. Other good practices that the PI may adopt to allow re-use and validation of data include (but are not limited to) making the pre-print version of articles openly accessible and publishing metadata and a link to the datasets on the website <https://fismproject.com>. The website will also be used by the PI as a tool to provide information on all public engagement and dissemination activities related to the project. It is also worth mentioning that, in addition to the FAIR principles, the PI is planning a correct use of the generated data, including aspects related to resource allocation, data security and ethical/legal aspects.

4. Other research outputs

At the present stage, the research does not entail the production of digital and physical outputs that would entail aspects related to the ownership of the results and possibility of patenting. Nevertheless, if, in the course of the research or after it, these types of outputs were to be produced, the beneficiaries will adopt a FAIR and OPEN approach. The limited access to the results of the project will be due only to reasons of exploitation of the results with a view to strengthening the European leadership in the sector in question. In particular, art. 17 of the AGA, it is stated that:

“unless providing open access would in particular:

- be against the beneficiary’s legitimate interests, including regarding commercial exploitation, or;
- be contrary to any other constraints, in particular the EU competitive interests or the beneficiary’s obligations under this Agreement; if open access is not provided (to some or all data), this must be justified in the DMP”

5. Allocation of resources

As far as the allocation of the resources in the project is concerned, the project entails the following direct and indirect costs, necessary for making data or other research outputs safe and FAIR:

1. The project entails the use of Zenodo, used as trusted repository to store all the data produced in the research. Zenodo can upload files up to 50 GB per dataset at no cost. The use of Zenodo also permits the researcher to assure to any of the generated data a DOI (Digital Object Identifier), making the data easily and freely citable and traceable.
2. The direct costs of archiving on pCloud, a software that provides data encryption options and password protection to access the files. It also offers an automatic backup feature. The annual cost of pCloud is 43,00 Euros, for a total cost over the course of three years of 129,00 Euros. The costs are to be considered VAT excluded.
3. The cost of purchasing Kaspersky Endpoint Security antivirus software. The annual cost is €34.00. Renewal is automatic and costs €54.99 per year. VAT not included.
4. The cost of purchasing two external hard drives to store the data associated with the WPs. Costs deriving from the purchase of two external hard-disk where data connected to the WPs are stocked.
5. The project may – but not necessarily will – entail indirect costs of counselling of a data manager, that supports and advises in the procedures of data management, access to the restricted data and other matters connected. The cost may vary between 250,00- and 1000,00-Euros pro year. The costs are to be considered VAT excluded.
6. The project may involve indirect costs for a legal advisor to advise on legal and ethical issues related to data protection in research. The costs may vary between 250,00 and 1000,00 euros per year. The costs are to be considered exclusive of VAT.
7. Throughout the process, the PI will be technically supported by a data science expert for the realization of tasks involving the use of AI. The counselling may entail indirect costs that may vary between 250,00 and 1000,00 euros pro year.
8. The publication on journals that do not publish in open access entails costs in the acquisition of the rights to publish in open access the pre-print, printed version of the texts in Zenodo. The costs vary according the nature and policy of the different journals and it is not possible to identify them in the current version of the DMP.

The costs connected to the archiving on pCloud, the costs of counselling of a data legal advisor will be directly covered by the researcher. Also, the costs for an advisor in data science will be covered by the researcher. The costs of consultancy services provided by a data manager to assist and advise on the management of research data/outputs, as well as those related to the acquisition of open access publishing rights, are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant and comply with the terms and conditions of the grant agreement. Regarding data management responsibilities, it should be noted that

the PI of the research will be responsible for the generation of data and metadata. Together with the research coordinator, the PI will be responsible for ensuring the quality, safety and compliance of the research with the FAIR principles. Throughout the research, the PI will be advised by an ethics mentor and a data manager, who will also assist the PI in ensuring that the research complies with the FAIR guidelines. The long-term preservation of data on Zenodo is guaranteed for five years after the end of the research. Indeed, the preservation of data and metadata in the years following the research will have several potential values. First and foremost, it will allow the re-use of the generated data and metadata for new research by the PI and other researchers. Policy makers, stakeholders and other institutions will also have the opportunity to re-use the data. The metadata will be preserved on Zenodo as long as this platform is supported. Data stored on external hard disks, if not essential for future research, will be deleted three years after the end of the project. Indeed, if the PI intends to maintain the security of the data (especially if the research generates sensitive data), it will be necessary to avoid keeping track of data that could be lost and, as a consequence, inappropriately accessed/used by others. Data will be stored on pCloud and will be kept for five years after the realisation of the project. The data will be stored in a computer of the beneficiary institution of the project, where it will be accessible only with a secret password known by the PI and the research coordinator. The costs of implementing this plan will be covered by the PI, and the decisions regarding the safe, ethical and compliant management of the data will be taken in collaboration with the ethics mentor and other individuals who guarantee the quality of data management. All decisions concerning the integrity and security of the data will be taken by the PI in collaboration with the coordinator and other individuals (ethics mentor, data manager) who contribute to ensuring the quality of the research.

6. Data security

The main principles of data security will be to ensure the integrity and security of the data during and after the completion of the project. At the same time, the following measures will be taken to enable the re-use of all data during and after the completion of the project. The data will be stored throughout the project at different scales:

1. First of all, on the researcher's computer. The computer will be accessible through a secret password and will be secured by the use of Kaspersky Endpoint Security.
2. On two external hard-disks; every hard-disk will be connected to the distinct datasets of the research.
3. On Zenodo, used as a trusted repository, where the data will be deposited up to five years after the completion of the research.
4. On pCloud, that provides data encryption options and password protection to access your files. It also offers an automatic backup feature.
5. On a beneficiary's computer (in a computer belonging to the department of host institution of the project). The access to the data will be possible only by password.

In addition to these measures, a variety of good practices will be followed during the data collection to ensure the security, integrity of the data. Among them, good practices will include (but will be limited to):

1. Daily backups of data to be performed on external drives and in the pCloud, which can also perform the backup automatically;
2. Use of passwords to protect all data generated during research and stored in virtual cloud storage and, if possible, on external hard drives;
3. Informing the researchers involved in the research (coordinator, ethics mentor, data manager) of the measures taken to maintain the security, safety and integrity of the data during the process; they will also be informed of the password to access the data;
4. Store data in digital cloud storage such as pCloud, which offers data encryption options and password protection to access your files;
5. On Zenodo and digital repositories, share access with responsible people, such as the coordinator, ethics mentor, data manager, who can provide access to the data (if restricted) if the PI is unable to perform this task alone;
6. Use systems that are protected by modern antivirus systems;
7. Delete all raw data on external hard disks that are not needed to complete the tasks and WPs as foreseen in the project.
8. Use sentinel and monitoring software, i.e. IDS (intrusion detection systems) and IPS (intrusion prevention systems);
9. Implement a security plan in advance that includes the times and methods for restoring normal functionality of IT systems following a DDoS, virus and/or ransomware attack;
10. Connect only the necessary PCs to the network.

7. Ethics

Ethical measures

According to the “Ethics summary report” the research reveals four kinds of ethical issues, concerning: 1) The realization of qualitative research that entails the presence of humans; 2) The generation of personal data through the realization of interviews, focus group and other qualitative research activities; 3) The realization of activities in non-EU countries; 4) The possible – but not required – use of a software of artificial intelligence to investigate data extracted from social media. The research may – but not necessarily will – also entail the generation of special categories of personal data (the ‘sensitive’ data). Special categories of personal data encompass data that “personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation” (Article 9(1) GDPR). This personal data may be generated especially in the production of video-recordings of the participants. Performers, activists and other participants may, indeed, express political, religious or philosophical beliefs. Moreover, it is worth considering that, according to the document “EU Grants: How to complete your ethics self-assessment”, even if they are not properly sensitive data, “more than minimum risks” connected to the research could derive from conducting qualitative research that implies activities connected to “potentially vulnerable individuals and groups”. These risks may be implicit in the WPs where data will be derived from interviews, videotaping and other activities that would involve the presence of participants belonging to minority groups. This is relevant for the research that implies the participation of authors belonging to Dalit, Adivasi, LGBTQIA+ communities. It also implies the participation of women belonging to these groups and communities.

In the light of these ethical issues, it is worth noting that the “Ethics summary report” declared the project to be “ethics ready”: it also recommended that the PI appoint an ethics mentor. The ethical issues mentioned above may have an impact on the sharing of data and the conditions of access to the data; in fact, especially in the case where sensitive personal data would be generated, it may be necessary to restrict access to Zenodo, which is used as a trusted repository, and make it available only to individuals who meet certain conditions (see conditions in section 3.2, “Making data accessible”). In addition, data sharing must follow the FAIR principle of the “as open as possible and as closed as necessary”: “open” in order to foster the reusability and to accelerate research, but also “closed” to safeguard the privacy of the subjects. The generation of new raw and processed data during activities that involve personal data will strictly follow the following ethical measures, which follow the norms and guidelines as indicated in Regulation EU 2016/679 (GDPR), in “Ethics and data protection” (2018), in the “EU Charter of Fundamental Rights” and in other documents that suggest best practices, especially in the field of humanities (Potnis, Gala 2020). The following measures will be strictly followed to minimize the risks connected to data protection but also to make the data FAIR:

1. In any phase of the research the PI will make all the *sensitive* data, unless differently requested by the participants, *anonymized*. Data which are *not sensitive* but that raise ethical concerns *may be pseudonymized*.
2. The generation of personal data will be possible only if the participants will accept the provisions of data collection as articulated in *informed data consents*. Participants should accept *two* data consents: one consent would treat the agreement to participate in the research. The second would concern ways in which data will be used in the research (data collection, processing, criteria of access and re-use).
3. “If the data processing entails potential risks to the data subjects’ rights and freedoms, they must be made aware of these risks during the informed consent procedure.” (Ethics and data protection, 2018: 11)
4. Pursuant to the guidelines as expressed in the “Ethics and data protection”, all the consents will be “informed” and contain 1. “the identity of the data controller and, where applicable, the contact details of the DPO”; 2. “the specific purpose(s) of the processing for which the personal data will be used”; 3. “the subject’s rights as guaranteed by the GDPR and the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights, in particular the right to withdraw consent or access their data, the procedures to follow should they wish to do so, and the right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority”; 4. information as to whether data will be shared with or transferred to third parties and for what purposes; and how long the data will be retained before they are destroyed; 5. The PI provides to the participants all the necessary information to contact him if they would live to cancel or rectify the conditions of use of the data.
5. To safeguard the protection of all the data that may imply ethical issues, all the video-recordings and images that may identify people will be collected and processed *only* at the condition that the participants would accept the conditions of collection, processing and re-use as expressed in the informed data consents.
6. The datasets that imply the presence of data that would produce ethical concerns will be stored on Zenodo, used as a trusted repository, with restricted access. The conditions for obtaining access have been already explained (see 3.2.). As a general rule, the PI will allow other users to get access to the data only after ascertaining the identity, the scientific scope behind the need to access the data and other useful information to check that the granting access would not produce risks to data protection.

7. With reference to the *purpose limitation* and *data minimization* the data will be collected only if this task will be absolutely necessary for the purposes specified in the project. Moreover, the storage of these data will happen only for purposes linked to the research (*storage limitation*). It must be also taken into consideration that the proponent will respect the general principle of accuracy of the data.

Following the recommendations as in the “Ethics summary report”, an ethics mentor has been appointed. Lorenza Acquarone, professor of “Indian Culture” at the Faculty of “Linguistic and Cultural Mediation Sciences” of the “University of Milan”, and lawyer, has accepted this role and will advise the PI during the project. This does not exclude the fact that the PI may decide in the future to appoint also other figures with this function. The PI will also be advised by Licia Proserpio, Adjunct Professor and Research Manager at the Department of History and Culture of the University of Bologna. In addition, in order to minimize the risks associated with the collection, processing and sharing of data, whenever they occur during the research, the PI, together with the project coordinator, will be involved in a number of actions:

1. Inform as soon as possible the European Commission about the entity of the risks and the damages to data protection.
2. Organize a meeting with the participants (or people in contact with them) as soon as possible to understand the nature of the problems.
3. Asking institutions and political actors in India and Europe (International Office at Sapienza, NGOs, Italian Embassy in India, etc.) to assist the PI in identifying policies to mitigate the risks/damages.
4. Organize initiatives to mitigate the identified problems, which may include economic and legal support.

With reference to WP4 of the project, named “Gathering and analysis of comedy-related sources on social-media and networks” (Dataset 4), the FISM plans the data collection and analysis of four hundred humorous memes published on Instagram public accounts. It is relevant to note that the PI plans to use one up to *three* different *legal* and *ethical* strategies of data extraction.

1. The first data collection strategy involves the use of the Instagram Graph API, an official non-AI programme for accessing data from Instagram in a compliant manner. The strategy of using the Instagram Graph API follows the following workflow: A) Creating an account on the platform; B) Obtaining access tokens; C) Obtaining API permissions; D) Defining the hashtags for data collection; E) Using the hashtag search endpoint to retrieve posts containing specific hashtags from public profiles. Example use case: Collect memes tagged with hashtags related to comedy; D) Filtering the content of posts. This strategy complies with Instagram's terms of service. Another advantage is that it is easy to implement.
2. The second strategy is manual data curation. This is the safest data analysis strategy. In fact, the PI can manually analyze all the data and avoid any bias that may be automatically generated by softwares and based on religious, gender or political dimensions. This research will also be conducted in accordance with Instagram's regulations. Manual curation does not provide the same precision as the other data collection techniques. However, it is a necessary and compulsory strategy to be used alone or in combination with the other two methods.
3. The third strategy (*optional*) implies the use of third-party AI tools that aggregate data from Instagram, in accordance with its policies. The PI will use Brandwatch (or equivalent AI software), which provides data collection on public profiles on Instagram. Brandwatch is compliant with Instagram's access rules, in particular with regard to its API and the platform's policies on data use and privacy. The advantage of this software is that it avoids violating Instagram's terms by not scraping data from private accounts.

At the conclusion of the data collection, the research implies a second research phase during which the PI plans to realize a data analysis of the previously generated raw data. Given the nature of the data, the analysis will be carried out primarily in a manual way by the PI. In addition, the research may require the use of AI software (Python or an equivalent ethical and robust software) to realize the textual analysis of the data, and the realization of the following workflow: A) data storage (all extracted data are stored in a structured format (CSV, JSON); B) data pre-processing, which may include tasks such as removing special characters, tokenization, stopword removal, etc.; C) text vectorization, which involves converting text data into numerical form for model training; E) model training, which will entail: splitting the dataset into training and test sets; for sentiment analysis, measure accuracy, precision, recall; human-in-command (HIC) approaches; F) Model evaluation; E) Model deployment and usage; F) interpretation of results.

In the light of the above, it is also possible to define some rules and ethical guidelines that the PI will follow for the data collection and analysis and, in particular, for the tasks that may involve the use of AI.

1. The AI software/s will be used in compliance with the “Artificial Intelligence Act” (from 1 August 2024), with the “Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI” (2019), with the “The Assessment List for Trustworthy

- Artificial Intelligence” (ALTAI, 2020) and, more in general, with provisions on data privacy and data protection (GDPR).
2. The AI software/s will be used in compliance with the regulations of Instagram, in particular to its policies on data use and privacy and the Instagram Graph API.
 3. All the software/s used will be lawful, ethical and robust. They will meet all the seven requirements that are indicated by the ALTAI guidelines and include: “Human agency and oversight”, “Technical robustness and safety”, Respect of ‘Privacy and data governance’, ‘Transparency’, ‘Societal and environment well-being’, ‘Accountability’.
 4. In order to meet the requirement of 'human agency and control' and to maintain “human agency and autonomy” (ALTAI, 7-8), the PI will take measures to minimize the risk of dependency and manipulation. The main measure is to use the AI software only for the specific, narrow objectives of the research.
 5. The PI will also use control mechanisms such as human-in-the-loop (HITL), human-on-the-loop (HOTL) or human-in-command (HIC) approaches.
 6. In order to maintain an HIC approach, the PI will, before deploying the AI, be committed to using techniques that allow the training of the adopted technology.
 7. In addition, at all stages of the research, the PI will monitor and filter all outputs produced by the AI and be alert to biases that may be produced by the AI in producing a classification through textual analysis. The PI will therefore correct the data in accordance with the ethical principles that inspire the research.
 8. The PI will use only public accounts and posts and avoid accessing private or restricted data.
 9. All the data will be minimized and anonymous.
 10. If the content of the memes would raise any kind of ethical concern, the PI may ask the author/s of the page a consent to generate raw and processed data during the research.
 11. Throughout the process, the PI will be technically supported by a data science expert for the realization of tasks involving the use of AI.
 12. If AI will be used in the course of WP4, the PI will provide detailed information about the methodology, the reasons behind the decision to use a specific software and any ethical concerns related to the use of AI. Conversely, if the PI decides not to use the software, he/she will explain in detail how and for what methodological, ethical reasons he/she rejected this option.

Finally, it is important to note that, as a general principle, the data analysis of memes from social media (even those that will not be investigated through by means of an AI software) will cover *always* and *only* a limited number of only public pages. The research, to protect the privacy, will also ensure that all the data will be analyzed in a collective and anonymized way.

Legal aspects

The described research activity must be included in the scope of application of the regulation on the processing of personal data, by Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR) pursuant to art. 1 of the same. In particular, pursuant to art. 2 of the GDPR, it “applies to the processing of personal data wholly or partly by automated means and to the processing other than by automated means of personal data which form part of a filing system or are intended to form part of a filing system.” As regards, then, the lawfulness of the processing of personal data, pursuant to art. 6, paragraph 1, letter a), of the GDPR, the processing can be legitimately carried out only if and to the extent that the interested party has expressed consent to the processing of his or her personal data for one or more specific purposes. In this general context, it is also worth remembering that, pursuant to art. 9 of the GDPR the processing of special categories of personal data is possible if “necessary for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes in accordance with Article 89 (1) based on Union or Member State law which shall be proportionate to the aim pursued, respect the essence of the right to data protection and provide for suitable and specific measures to safeguard the fundamental rights and the interests of the data subject.” The Indian legislation contained in the Digital Personal Data Protection Act (D.P.D.P.A), approved on 11 August 2023, is of the same tenor and in regulating the matter does not appear to differ from European legislation. In particular, pursuant to art. 17, second paragraph, of the DPDPA “The provisions of this Act shall not apply in respect of the processing of personal data [...] necessary for research, archiving or statistical purposes if the personal data is not to be used to take any specific decision to a Data Principal and such processing is carried out in accordance with such standards as may be prescribed”. Pursuant to art. 4 of the DPDPA, “A person may process the personal data of a Data Principal only in accordance with the provisions of this Act and for a lawful purpose: (a) for which the Data Principal has given her consent; or (b) for certain legitimate uses”.

8. Other issues

Beside the above-mentioned regulations and ethical guidelines, the PI is aware also of other fundamental international legislation that regulate data management. Among them, the PI is aware of the following legislations:

- Nuremberg Code (1947) addressing volunteer consent and proper acting;
- The declaration of Helsinki in its last version of 2013;
- The charter of Fundamental rights of the EU Directive 95/46/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 October 1995.
- Personal data protection legislations. In India the personal data protection is governed by two laws, that are the Personal Data Protection Bill (PDPB) 2019 and the Information Technology (Reasonable Security Practices and Procedures and Sensitive Personal Data or Information) Rules, 2011.
- Copyright law in India is governed by the Copyright Act, 1957 (amended 2012), which provides legal protection to authors of original works, including literary, artistic, musical and cinematographic works.

HISTORY OF CHANGES		
VERSION	PUBLICATION DATE	CHANGE
1.0	28.12.2024	Initial version